

An Analytical Design Framework for Dimensioning Solar-powered Green IoT Nodes

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Abstract—The rapid adoption of the Internet of Things (IoT) across various industries has significantly enhanced productivity and efficiency. However, the widespread deployment of battery-powered IoT devices raises concerns about energy sustainability, battery longevity, and environmental impact. Frequent battery replacements pose logistical challenges, particularly in large-scale networks and remote locations. To address these issues, the Green IoT (G-IoT) design framework has been introduced, emphasizing energy-efficient strategies such as duty cycling, transceiver optimization, energy-aware routing, and the integration of renewable energy sources like photovoltaic (PV) energy harvesting. Despite advancements in G-IoT, a major challenge remains: the dynamic and unpredictable nature of both IoT energy consumption and harvested energy. In this paper, we propose a design framework for Green IoT that models the interplay between energy harvesting, storage, and consumption processes. By incorporating time-varying energy dynamics, the proposed framework enables efficient dimensioning of energy harvesters and storage systems, ensuring optimal energy management in IoT networks. This approach allows for the evaluation of various energy-saving strategies and enhances the long-term sustainability of IoT deployments. Numerical examples and simulation results demonstrate the effectiveness of the framework in maintaining energy balance and extending the operational lifetime of IoT nodes.

Index Terms—Green IoT (G-IoT), Analytical Design Framework, Solar-powered G-IoT nodes, energy storage systems, energy optimisation.

I. INTRODUCTION

The adoption of the Internet of Things (IoT) has been rapidly increasing across various industries, including agriculture, transportation, energy, home automation, manufacturing, security, healthcare, and the military. IoT technology enhances productivity and efficiency by enabling real-time monitoring, automation, and data-driven decision-making. Over the past two decades, tens of billions of IoT devices have been deployed, with projections indicating the deployment of hundreds of billions more in the coming years. However, this exponential growth raises significant concerns about the environmental impact and sustainability of IoT systems.

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Most IoT devices rely on compact, cost-effective batteries with limited energy storage capacity [1]. A major drawback of battery-powered IoT devices is that once the stored energy is depleted, the device ceases to function. The logistical challenges associated with battery replacement—especially in large-scale IoT networks and remote or hard-to-reach locations—can be considerable in terms of cost, time, and labor. For instance, replacing batteries in IoT nodes deployed for soil or crop monitoring in large agricultural fields or for pipeline monitoring along vast distances is both costly and technically challenging. Consequently, there is an urgent need to design and deploy IoT networks capable of operating for extended periods, ideally several years, before requiring battery replacements [2]. Additionally, the disposal of used batteries presents an environmental challenge, further emphasizing the need for sustainable energy solutions.

To address these concerns, the Green IoT (G-IoT) design framework [3], [4] has been introduced as a strategy for developing energy-efficient and sustainable IoT systems. G-IoT emphasizes minimizing energy consumption in IoT nodes and increasing the integration of renewable energy sources to extend operational lifetimes without frequent energy-related interventions. Several techniques have been proposed under the G-IoT framework, including duty cycling, transceiver optimization, energy-aware routing, adaptive sensing, protocol overhead reduction, and voltage and frequency control. Additionally, low-power communication technologies such as BLE, RFID, NFC, Zigbee, LoRa, and Sigfox have been adopted to enhance energy efficiency [5]. Another promising approach involves the use of energy harvesting systems, such as photovoltaic (PV) panels, to harness ambient energy and replenish depleted battery reserves.

A key challenge in designing green IoT nodes is that their energy consumption often fluctuates over time, particularly in event-driven applications such as pipeline monitoring and geofencing [6]. Similarly, energy harvested from renewable sources, such as solar radiation, is inherently stochastic, varying throughout the day and across different seasons [7], [8]. Therefore, achieving a balance between energy harvesting, storage, and consumption is crucial to ensure the long-term sustainability and reliability of IoT systems.

Several studies have explored energy-efficient IoT design methodologies. The authors in [9] proposed a model-based systems design methodology for G-IoT, employing multi-

physical co-simulation in a virtual environment to optimize energy consumption. The work in [10] presented an empirical approach for designing solar-powered IoT nodes, while [11] introduced a micro-scale solar power management architecture for self-powered IoT nodes, demonstrating how properly sized solar panels and low-power devices enhance sustainability. Furthermore, [12] discussed various energy-saving, energy-balancing, and energy-harvesting strategies for green wireless sensor networks.

Energy harvesting is a fundamental strategy for Green IoT, enabling devices to harness energy from ambient renewable sources such as solar (photovoltaic), radio frequency (RF) signals, wind, and mechanical vibrations. However, ensuring a stable energy supply is challenging due to the unpredictable and intermittent nature of these sources [13]. Moreover, the amount of energy harvested by IoT devices is often minimal, typically ranging from a few hundred milliwatt-hours (mWh) to as little as a few hundred micro-watt-hours (μWh). This limitation highlights the need for effective energy management strategies to optimize device performance. A comprehensive review of energy harvesting techniques for Green IoT can be found in [12], [14].

The most widely used analytical frameworks for modeling the performance and reliability of Green IoT (G-IoT) systems are based on the energy packet concept [15], [16], where an energy packet represents a power pulse with a finite energy value. In this approach, the energy storage capacity of the energy storage system (ESS), as well as the energy harvesting and consumption processes, are discretized into energy packets. Queueing theory-based models are then employed to estimate key performance metrics such as the mean number of stored energy packets, service outage probability, and device lifetime. A more detailed exploration of this concept can be found in [17]–[19].

Alternatively, energy variations within an ESS can be modeled as a continuous stochastic process. This includes fluid flow models [20]–[22] and diffusion-based models [23]–[26], which provide a different perspective on energy dynamics and system performance. Existing studies have a key limitation: they fail to fully capture the dynamic interaction between energy harvesting and consumption processes. Understanding this interaction is crucial, as time-dependent variations in these stochastic processes directly influence the fluctuations in the energy content of the storage system. Without accounting for these dynamics, the impact of temporal changes in energy availability and demand remains inadequately addressed.

Despite advancements in G-IoT design, there remains a pressing need for a comprehensive IoT design framework that facilitates the optimal dimensioning of energy harvesters and storage systems while accounting for dynamic fluctuations in energy harvesting and consumption. Such a framework would allow researchers and engineers to evaluate different energy management strategies and protocols before implementing them in real-world IoT deployments.

In this paper, we propose and analyze a design framework for Green IoT that models the dynamic interaction between en-

Fig. 1. The architecture of a green IoT node.

ergy harvesting, energy storage, and energy consumption. This framework provides valuable insights into optimizing energy usage in IoT networks, ensuring long-term sustainability and reliability.

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

We consider a green IoT node consisting of an IoT sensor node, an energy harvester, and an energy storage system. The IoT sensor node comprises a processing unit, such as a microcontroller unit (MCU), central processing unit (CPU), graphics processing unit (GPU), or network processing unit (NPU), along with a communication unit and various sensor devices connected to its communication ports.

We adopt the harvest-store-use energy harvesting protocol [27], where energy is first harvested and stored in an energy storage system before being used to power the IoT node. The energy storage system, which may be a battery or a supercapacitor, has a limited capacity denoted as B .

Two functional scenarios are considered: In the first case, the IoT node operates on a predefined schedule, waking up at specific times to collect sensor data and transmit it to a fog or cloud computing server via an access point. A typical example is a smart water meter that wakes up at 6 AM and 6 PM to record and transmit measurements. Other applications include IoT nodes used in smart agriculture, intelligent transportation systems, and smart manufacturing. We refer to this category as a schedule-driven IoT node.

In the second case, the IoT node wakes up at random intervals, triggered by external events. This is relevant for IoT applications that require real-time monitoring, such as pipeline surveillance systems, where the node activates whenever a vibration is detected [6]. This type of node is referred to as an event-triggered IoT node.

We focus on solar-powered IoT nodes, which are particularly suitable for outdoor applications, such as smart agricul-

ture, pipeline monitoring, and intelligent transportation systems. These nodes require additional components, including direct current (DC) converters for power adaptation and energy management systems for optimizing energy usage.

III. IOT ENERGY CONSUMPTION MODELS

To conserve energy, an IoT node is typically placed in sleep or deep sleep mode when it is idle. In other words, if the node is not engaged in sensing, computing, or communication tasks, it is transitioned into a low-power state. Consequently, the total energy consumption of the device depends on the duration it spends in active mode—where it performs sensing, computing, or communication operations—and the time it remains in sleep mode throughout its operational lifetime, from deployment until its energy is fully depleted and it shuts down. The total energy consumption of the IoT node is given by:

$$E_{\text{total}}^{\text{node}} = \sum_{i=1}^N P_i^{\text{node}} \cdot \Delta t \quad (1)$$

where: E_{total} is the total energy consumed over the simulation period (in Wh), P_i^{node} is the power consumption at time step i (in W), Δt is the time step duration (in hours), N is the total number of time steps.

For each time step, the node consumes power P_{sleep} in sleep mode (the node remains in low-power mode when not active) and consumes power P_{active} during active periods. When an IoT device wakes up to take measurements and transmit data, the total active time per wake-up cycle depends on the time spent in each active state. These states include sensing (when the node collects data), receiving (when the node processes control or synchronization packets), transmitting (when the node sends data), and idle (when the node remains active but not engaged in any task). The total active time per wake-up cycle is given by:

$$T_{\text{active}} = T_{\text{sensing}} + P_{\text{processing}} + T_{\text{rx}} + T_{\text{tx}} + T_{\text{idle}}. \quad (2)$$

Similarly, the power consumed during each wake-up cycle is:

$$P_{\text{active}} = P_{\text{sensing}} + P_{\text{processing}} + P_{\text{rx}} + P_{\text{tx}} + P_{\text{idle}}. \quad (3)$$

The power consumption and duration of operation depend on the IoT device, the communication protocol, and the specific application scenario. The energy consumption pattern, or power profile, of an IoT node can be characterized through simulations or empirical measurements. The time required to transmit an IoT packet is determined by the packet size and channel capacity as follows:

$$T_{\text{tx}} = \frac{m \cdot 8}{C}, \quad (4)$$

where m is the size of the transmitted data packet (in bytes) and C is the data transmission rate (in bits per second).

According to Shannon's information and communication theory, the energy required to transmit an IoT data packet of size m bytes with transmission power P_{tx} is given by [28]:

$$\epsilon = (\eta \cdot P_{\text{tx}} + P_0) \frac{m \cdot 8}{W \log_2(1 + \text{SNR})}, \quad (5)$$

Fig. 2. Power consumption profile of an IoT node over a 7-day period.

where η is the power amplifier's efficiency factor, and P_0 represents the electronic power consumption overhead. The term W denotes the channel bandwidth, while the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is defined as:

$$\text{SNR} = \frac{P_{\text{rx}}}{P_I + P_N}, \quad (6)$$

where P_{rx} is the received power, P_I is the interference power, and P_N is the noise power. The signal transmitted by the IoT device undergoes attenuation as it propagates through the channel, and the power received at the base station is given by:

$$P_{\text{rx}} = P_L \cdot P_{\text{tx}}. \quad (7)$$

Here, P_{tx} is the transmit power, and the path loss P_L is defined in [28]. Therefore, the total energy consumed for the purpose of transmitting data packets is

$$E_{\text{total}}^{\text{tx}} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_T} \epsilon_i \quad (8)$$

where N_T is the total number of transmitted data packets.

A. Regular power consumption model

Consider an IoT node that wakes up at 6 AM and 6 PM, remains active for 6 minutes per wake-up, and then returns to sleep mode. The total active time per day is:

$$T_{\text{daily}} = 2 \times T_{\text{active}}. \quad (9)$$

For a simulation period of N days, the total active time is:

$$T_{\text{total}} = N \times T_{\text{daily}}. \quad (10)$$

Figures 2 and 3 illustrate the power profile of an IoT node that wakes up at 6 AM and 6 PM to take measurements and transmit data via a low-power communication channel.

The simulation parameters are as follows:

- Number of simulation days: $N_{\text{days}} = 7$.
- Total simulation time: $N_{\text{total hours}} = 24 \times N_{\text{days}}$.
- Time step resolution: $\Delta t = 0.01$ hours (36 seconds).
- Power consumption for different states: sleep mode: $P_{\text{sleep}} = 0.5$ mW, sensing mode: $P_{\text{sensing}} = 5$ mW, transmitting mode: $P_{\text{tx}} = 50$ mW, receiving mode: $P_{\text{rx}} = 20$ mW.

Fig. 3. Snapshot of the power consumption profile of an IoT node, highlighting power levels for different operational states (Sensing → Transmitting → Idle → Receiving → Sleeping).

- Wake-up duration: 6 minutes per cycle, with: sensing: $T_{\text{sensing}} = 1$ min, transmitting: $T_{\text{tx}} = 3$ mins, idle: $T_{\text{idle}} = 1$ min, and receiving: $T_{\text{rx}} = 2$ mins.

Figure 2 reveals a pattern of periodic power pulses at 6 AM and 6 PM each day, indicating active wake-up periods. The power profile is similar to the measured power profile of an IoT node presented in [10]. Figure 3 provides a detailed snapshot, highlighting power levels associated with each operational state.

B. Event-triggered power consumption model

Consider an IoT node that remains in low-power sleep mode until activated by an external event (e.g., detecting a leakage in pipeline monitoring). Upon activation, the node wakes up, collects sensor data, processes the information, transmits or receives communication packets, and then returns to sleep. The time intervals between consecutive wake-up events are modeled as a Poisson process, meaning the time between events follows an exponential distribution with a rate parameter λ_{wake} . In this case, the total energy consumption of the IoT node over a simulation period can be formulated as:

$$E_{\text{total}}^{\text{node}} = \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{wake}}} E_{\text{wake}} + E_{\text{sleep}} \quad (11)$$

where: $E_{\text{total}}^{\text{node}}$ is the total energy consumed over N_{days} , N_{wake} is the total number of wake-up events, E_{wake} is the energy consumed per wake-up cycle, and E_{sleep} is the energy consumed in sleep mode.

During each wake-up event, the node transitions through different power states. The energy consumption for each state is given by:

$$E_{\text{state}} = P_{\text{state}} \times T_{\text{state}} \quad (12)$$

where P_{state} and T_{state} are the power consumption and duration of each state, respectively.

Thus, the total energy consumption per wake-up cycle is:

$$E_{\text{wake}} = P_{\text{sensing}}T_{\text{sensing}} + P_{\text{tx}}T_{\text{tx}} + P_{\text{idle}}T_{\text{idle}} + P_{\text{rx}}T_{\text{rx}} \quad (13)$$

Fig. 4. Event-triggered Power consumption profile of an IoT node over a 7-day period.

Since the wake-ups follow an exponential distribution with rate λ_{wake} , the expected number of wake-ups per day is λ_{wake} , and the total energy consumed over N_{days} is:

$$E_{\text{active, total}} = N_{\text{wake}} \times E_{\text{wake}} \quad (14)$$

The node remains in sleep mode when not active. The energy consumed in sleep mode is:

$$E_{\text{sleep}} = P_{\text{sleep}} \times (T_{\text{total}} - N_{\text{wake}}T_{\text{active}}) \quad (15)$$

where: $T_{\text{total}} = 24 \times N_{\text{days}}$ (total simulation time), and T_{active} is the total duration of an active period.

The final expression for the total energy consumption is:

$$E_{\text{total}} = N_{\text{wake}} (P_{\text{sensing}}T_{\text{sensing}} + P_{\text{tx}}T_{\text{tx}} + P_{\text{idle}}T_{\text{idle}} + P_{\text{rx}}T_{\text{rx}}) + P_{\text{sleep}} \times (24N_{\text{days}} - N_{\text{wake}}T_{\text{active}}) \quad (16)$$

The power profile of an event-triggered IoT node is shown in Fig. 4. The simulation parameters remain consistent with those used in Figs. 2 and 3. The average number of events per day is set to $\lambda_{\text{wake}} = 3$, meaning the node wakes up based on a Poisson-distributed event occurrence. Unlike Fig. 2, where wake-up intervals are regular, the time between power pulses here is irregular. As a result, energy consumption fluctuates, increasing with higher event frequency and decreasing when fewer events occur. This variability makes it challenging to predict the node's energy demand accurately.

IV. DIMENSIONING OF IOT SOLAR ENERGY HARVESTING SYSTEMS

The energy harvesting system models the power generation of a solar panel under dynamic weather conditions using a Markov chain. The total energy output depends on solar radiation, weather states, temperature variations, and solar panel efficiency.

The natural daily variation of solar irradiance, peaking at midday and reaching zero at sunrise and sunset can be modeled using a sinusoidal equation [7], [8]:

$$I(t) = I_{\text{max}} \sin\left(\frac{\pi t}{L}\right) \quad (17)$$

where: t represents time based on the sampling period, $I(t)$ is the solar irradiance at time t , I_{\max} is the maximum solar irradiance recorded on the previous day, and L denotes the length of the day in terms of the sampling period.

Therefore, the solar radiation considered follows a sinusoidal pattern with positive values between the sunrise time t_{rise} and the sunset time t_{set} . The values of the solar radiation before 6 AM and 6 PM is zero. Thus, the solar radiation is given by:

$$I_{\text{solar}}(t) = I_{\text{SC}} \times \max\left(\sin\left(\frac{\pi(t - t_{rise})}{t_{set} - t_{rise}}\right), 0\right) \quad (18)$$

where: $I_{\text{solar}}(t)$ is the instantaneous solar radiation (W/m^2), $I_{\text{SC}} = 1361 W/m^2$ is the solar constant, t is the time in hours. In reality, the solar irradiance fluctuates randomly as the weather fluctuates throughout the day, requiring that a random process that governs the changes in the solar irradiance be incorporated into the solar energy harvesting model.

To model complex weather variations, a Markov chain is employed to simulate transitions between different weather states. Previous studies [27] have utilized a four-state Markov chain for this purpose. In this work, we adopt a three-state weather model with the state space:

$$\mathcal{S} = \{\text{Sunny, Cloudy, Rainy}\}$$

The weather state transitions are governed by a stochastic process, represented by the following transition rate matrix:

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} 0.7 & 0.3 & 0.0 \\ 0.5 & 0.4 & 0.1 \\ 0.2 & 0.3 & 0.5 \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

Where each element of the transition rate matrix represents the probabilities, p_{ij} of moving from one state i to another state j at each time step. For example, the probability of transitioning from the sunny state to the cloudy state is 30%. The weather states are mapped to corresponding solar radiation adjustments, affecting how much sunlight the panel receives. We consider the following mapping

$$W_{\text{eff}} = \begin{cases} 1.0 & (\text{Sunny: } 100\% \text{ of the solar radiation}) \\ 0.6 & (\text{Cloudy: } 60\% \text{ of the solar radiation}) \\ 0.3 & (\text{Rainy: } 30\% \text{ of the solar radiation}) \end{cases} \quad (20)$$

Thus, the adjusted solar radiation is:

$$I_{\text{adj}}(t) = I_{\text{solar}}(t) \times W_{\text{eff}}(t) \quad (21)$$

Temperature oscillates as:

$$T(t) = 25 + 5 \sin\left(\frac{\pi t}{24}\right) \quad (22)$$

Efficiency degradation due to temperature is modeled as:

$$\eta_{\text{adj}}(t) = \eta_{\text{panel}} \times (1 - 0.003(T(t) - 25)) \quad (23)$$

The energy output at time t is given by:

$$P_{\text{out}}(t) = I_{\text{adj}}(t) \times A_{\text{panel}} \times \eta_{\text{adj}}(t) \quad (24)$$

Fig. 5. Simulated Solar Panel Energy Output Over 24 hours with Markov Chain Weather Effects.

Fig. 6. Simulated Solar Panel Energy Output Over 2 Days with Markov Chain Weather Effects.

where: $A_{\text{panel}} = 0.001 m^2$ (panel area), $\eta_{\text{panel}} = 0.18$ (nominal efficiency), and $P_{\text{out}}(t)$ is in Watts.

In the simulation, the current state of the Markov chain is updated at each time step according to the transition matrix, and the weather state for each hour is recorded. The energy output is adjusted based on the simulated weather conditions. Total energy harvested over a period T is:

$$E_{\text{total}} = \sum_{t=1}^T P_{\text{out}}(t) \times \Delta t \quad (25)$$

where $\Delta t = 1$ hour.

The above analysis provides an accurate and dynamic estimation of solar energy harvesting while incorporating real-world variations in sunlight, weather, and temperature. The energy output of the energy harvester is shown in Figs. 5 and 6 shows the variation of the energy output of an IoT energy harvester. It grows from 6 AM, peaks at midday (12 PM), and then decreases to zero by 6 PM.

V. ENERGY DYNAMICS IN IOT ENERGY STORAGE SYSTEMS

We assume an ideal energy storage system with no energy losses due to leakage. While this simplifies the analysis and simulation process, it does not always hold in practice. Energy storage systems, such as batteries and supercapacitors, experience energy leakage, which can impact overall efficiency.

Fig. 7. The interaction between energy harvesting, storage, and consumption processes over 160 hours and the solar panel area, $A_{\text{panel}} = 0.1$ in square meters.

Notably, the leakage in supercapacitors increases exponentially with the stored energy, as discussed in [29]–[32]. The energy balance equation for the battery is given by:

$$E_{\text{battery}}(t+1) = E_{\text{battery}}(t) + E_{\text{harvested}}(t) - E_{\text{consumed}}(t) \quad (26)$$

where: $E_{\text{battery}}(t)$ is the battery energy level at time t (mWh). $E_{\text{harvested}}(t)$ is the energy harvested from the solar panel at time t :

$$E_{\text{harvested}}(t) = I_{\text{solar}}(t) \times A_{\text{panel}} \times \eta_{\text{panel}} \times \frac{\Delta t}{60} \times 1000 \quad (27)$$

where $I_{\text{solar}}(t)$ is the solar irradiance (Wh/m²), A_{panel} is the panel area (m²), η_{panel} is the panel efficiency, and Δt is the time step (minutes). The factor 1000 converts Wh to mWh. $E_{\text{consumed}}(t)$ is the energy consumption:

$$E_{\text{consumed}}(t) = P_{\text{mode}}(t) \times \frac{\Delta t}{60} \quad (28)$$

where $P_{\text{mode}}(t)$ is the power consumption based on the IoT node's state.

The battery level is constrained by:

$$0 \leq E_{\text{battery}}(t) \leq E_{\text{battery, max}} \quad (29)$$

where $E_{\text{battery, max}}$ is the maximum battery capacity.

Figs. 7 and 8 illustrate the dynamic interaction between energy harvesting, storage, and consumption processes. The nominal battery capacity considered is $Q = 2400$ mAh, with a corresponding voltage of $V = 3.7$ V. The solar irradiance data used in this analysis is based on the average daily values for each month in Bydgoszcz, obtained from [33].

In Fig. 7, the solar panel area is set to $A_{\text{panel}} = 0.1$ m². Although the energy harvested by the solar panel partially replenishes the energy depleted from the storage system, the overall battery energy level continuously declines over time. This occurs because the harvested energy is insufficient to fully compensate for the energy consumed by the system. The amount of energy harvested at time t depends on the solar

Fig. 8. The interaction between energy harvesting, storage, and consumption processes over 160 hours and the solar panel area, $A_{\text{panel}} = 0.5$ in square meters.

radiation intensity (which varies with weather conditions) and the solar panel area.

In Fig. 8, the solar panel area is increased to $A_{\text{panel}} = 0.5$ m². In this case, a sufficient amount of energy is harvested during daylight hours to replenish the energy depleted during nighttime periods. Although there are significant fluctuations in the battery's energy level, the overall battery charge remains consistently high, ensuring stable operation of the system.

One limitation of the proposed framework is its computational cost. With a small time resolution of $\Delta t = 1$ minute and a simulation duration of 5000 days, the execution time can exceed an hour, raising scalability concerns. However, in most practical scenarios, such long simulation times are rarely necessary for energy planning or dimensioning of G-IoT systems.

VI. CONCLUSION

The increasing deployment of IoT devices across various industries necessitates energy-efficient and sustainable design strategies. Traditional battery-powered IoT nodes face significant challenges, including limited operational lifetimes and logistical difficulties in battery replacement. To address these issues, Green IoT (G-IoT) frameworks have emerged, emphasizing low-power operation, energy-aware communication protocols, and renewable energy harvesting. However, the dynamic nature of both energy consumption and harvested energy introduces complexities in achieving long-term energy sustainability.

In this paper, we proposed a design framework for Green IoT, which models the interplay between energy harvesting, storage, and consumption processes. Our simulation results demonstrate how different IoT operational modes—periodic wake-up vs. event-triggered operation—impact energy consumption. Figures 2 and 3 reveal that periodic wake-up schedules generate predictable power pulses, while event-triggered operation (Fig. 4) leads to variable energy consumption patterns, making power management more challenging.

Furthermore, our analysis of solar energy harvesting shows that small solar panels (0.1 m²) may not generate enough energy to sustain IoT nodes continuously (Fig. 7), whereas larger panels (0.5 m²) enable energy self-sufficiency (Fig. 8).

These findings highlight the importance of accurately dimensioning energy harvesters and storage systems based on the specific energy needs and environmental conditions of an IoT deployment. The proposed framework provides a dynamic and accurate method for evaluating energy sustainability, allowing designers to optimize IoT systems before real-world implementation. Future work will focus on refining energy prediction models and integrating adaptive power management strategies to further enhance IoT sustainability and efficiency.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Al Homssi, A. Al-Hourani, S. Chandrasekharan, K. M. Gomez, and S. Kandeepan, "On the bound of energy consumption in cellular iot networks," *IEEE Transactions on Green Communications and Networking*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 355–364, 2019.
- [2] G. S. Kuaban, T. Czachórski, E. Gelenbe, S. Sharma, P. Singh, P. Pecka, V. Nkemeni, and P. Czekalski, "Energy performance of self-powered green iot nodes," *Frontiers in Energy Research*, in print, 2024.
- [3] A. Al-Ansi, A. M. Al-Ansi, A. Muthanna, I. A. Elgendy, and A. Koucheryavy, "Survey on intelligence edge computing in 6g: Characteristics, challenges, potential use cases, and market drivers," *Future Internet*, vol. 13, no. 5, 2021.
- [4] K. Sadatdiyev, L. Cui, L. Zhang, J. Z. Huang, S. Salloum, and M. S. Mahmud, "A review of optimization methods for computation offloading in edge computing networks," *Digital Communications and Networks*, vol. 9, no. 2, pp. 450–461, 2023.
- [5] M. H. Alsharif, A. Jahid, A. H. Kelechi, and R. Kannadasan, "Green iot: A review and future research directions," *Symmetry*, vol. 15, no. 3, p. 757, 2023.
- [6] G. S. Kuaban, T. Czachórski, E. Gelenbe, P. Pecka, V. Nkemeni, and P. Czekalski, "Energy performance of internet of things (iot) networks for pipeline monitoring," in *Proceedings of the 20th International Wireless Communications and Mobile Computing Conference (IWCMC 2024)*. IEEE, 2024.
- [7] M. Hassanzadeh, M. Etezadi-Amoli, and M. Fadali, "Practical approach for sub-hourly and hourly prediction of pv power output," in *North American Power Symposium 2010*. IEEE, 2010, pp. 1–5.
- [8] T. Sung, S. Y. Yoon, and K. C. Kim, "A mathematical model of hourly solar radiation in varying weather conditions for a dynamic simulation of the solar organic rankine cycle," *energies*, vol. 8, no. 7, pp. 7058–7069, 2015.
- [9] K. Majetta, J. Bräunig, C. Sohrmann, R. Jancke, and D. Mayer, "Model-based systems design for green iot systems," in *SMARTGREENS*, 2021, pp. 204–211.
- [10] J. Anzola, A. Jiménez, and G. Tarazona, "Self-sustainable power-collecting node in iot," *Internet of Things*, vol. 7, p. 100082, 2019.
- [11] S. Mondal and R. Paily, "Efficient solar power management system for self-powered iot node," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems I: Regular Papers*, vol. 64, no. 9, pp. 2359–2369, 2017.
- [12] V. Nkemeni, F. Mieyeville, G. S. Kuaban, P. Czekalski, K. Tokarz, W. B. Nsanyuy, E. M. Deussom Djomadji, M. L. Katche, P. Tsafack, and B. Zieliński, "Evaluation of green strategies for prolonging the lifespan of linear wireless sensor networks," *Sensors*, vol. 24, no. 21, p. 7024, 2024.
- [13] A. Kansal, J. Hsu, S. Zahedi, and M. B. Srivastava, "Power management in energy harvesting sensor networks," *ACM Transactions on Embedded Computing Systems (TECS)*, vol. 6, no. 4, pp. 32–es, 2007.
- [14] T. Sanislav, G. D. Mois, S. Zeadally, and S. C. Folea, "Energy harvesting techniques for internet of things (iot)," *IEEE access*, vol. 9, pp. 39 530–39 549, 2021.
- [15] E. Gelenbe, "Energy packet networks: Ict based energy allocation and storage," in *International Conference on Green Communications and Networking*. Springer, 2011, pp. 186–195.
- [16] —, "Energy packet networks: adaptive energy management for the cloud," in *CloudCP'12: Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop on Cloud Computing Platforms*. ACM, <https://doi.org/10.1145/2168697.2168698>, 2012, pp. 1–5.
- [17] E. Gelenbe and Y. M. Kadioglu, "Energy loss through standby and leakage in energy harvesting wireless sensors," in *2015 IEEE 20th International Workshop on Computer Aided Modelling and Design of Communication Links and Networks (CAMAD)*. IEEEXplore, 2015, pp. 231–236.
- [18] Y. M. Kadioglu and E. Gelenbe, "Product-form solution for cascade networks with intermittent energy," *IEEE Systems Journal*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 918–927, 2019.
- [19] G. S. Kuaban, T. Czachórski, E. Gelenbe, S. Sharma, and P. Czekalski, "A markov model for a self-powered green iot device with state-dependent energy consumption," in *2023 4th International Conference on Communications, Information, Electronic and Energy Systems (CIEES)*, 2023, pp. 1–7.
- [20] A. Gautam and S. Dharmaraja, "An analytical model driven by fluid queue for battery life time of a user equipment in LTE-A networks," *Physical Communication*, vol. 30, pp. 213–219, 2018.
- [21] G. L. Jones, P. G. Harrison, U. Harder, and T. Field, "Fluid queue models of battery life," in *Proceeding of the 2011 IEEE 19th Annual International Symposium on Modelling, Analysis, and Simulation of Computer and Telecommunication Systems*. IEEE, 2011, pp. 278–285.
- [22] C. Tunc and N. Akar, "Markov fluid queue model of an energy harvesting IoT device with adaptive sensing," *Performance Evaluation*, vol. 111, pp. 1–16, 2017.
- [23] T. Czachórski, E. Gelenbe, and G. S. Kuaban, "Modelling energy changes in the energy harvesting battery of an iot device," in *Proceedings of the 2022 30th International Symposium on Modeling, Analysis, and Simulation of Computer and Telecommunication Systems (MASCOTS)*. Nice, France: IEEE, 2022, pp. 81–88.
- [24] T. Czachórski, E. Gelenbe, G. S. Kuaban, and D. Marek, "Energy optimization for an unmanned aerial vehicle (e.g drone) during its mission," in *Security in Computer and Information Sciences. EuroCybersec 2021. Communications in Computer and Information Science*, vol. 1596. Springer, 2022, pp. 61–75.
- [25] E. Gelenbe and Y. M. Kadioglu, "Battery attacks on sensors: Wireless nodes with battery attacks," in *EuroCybersec 2018: International symposium on computer and information sciences, cybersecurity workshop*. Springer Cham, 2018.
- [26] G. S. Kuaban, E. Gelenbe, T. Czachórski, P. Czekalski, and J. K. Tangka, "Modelling of the energy depletion process and battery depletion attacks for battery-powered internet of things (iot) devices," *Sensors*, vol. 23, no. 13, 2023.
- [27] A. Jaitawat and A. K. Singh, "Battery and supercapacitor imperfections modeling and comparison for rf energy harvesting wireless sensor network," *Wireless Networks*, vol. 26, pp. 843–853, 2020.
- [28] B. A. Homssi, A. Al-Hourani, S. Chandrasekharan, K. M. Gomez, and S. Kandeepan, "On the bound of energy consumption in cellular iot networks," *IEEE Transactions on Green Communications and Networking*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 355–364, 2019.
- [29] G. V. Merrett, A. S. Weddell, A. P. Lewis, N. R. Harris, B. M. Al-Hashimi, and N. M. White, "An empirical energy model for supercapacitor powered wireless sensor nodes," in *2008 Proceedings of 17th International Conference on Computer Communications and Networks*. IEEE, 2008, pp. 1–6.
- [30] H. Yang and Y. Zhang, "Evaluation of supercapacitor models for wireless sensor network applications," in *2011 5th International Conference on Signal Processing and Communication Systems (ICSPCS)*, 2011, pp. 1–6.
- [31] A. S. Weddell, G. V. Merrett, T. J. Kazmierski, and B. M. Al-Hashimi, "Accurate supercapacitor modeling for energy harvesting wireless sensor nodes," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems II: Express Briefs*, vol. 58, no. 12, pp. 911–915, 2011.
- [32] G. S. Kuaban, T. Czachórski, E. Gelenbe, P. Pecka, V. Nkemeni, and P. Czekalski, "Impact of energy leakage on the energy performance of green iot nodes," in *2024 32nd International Conference on Modeling, Analysis and Simulation of Computer and Telecommunication Systems (MASCOTS)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 1–8.
- [33] "Climate and average weather year round in bydgoszcz poland," accessed on February. 15, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://weatherspark.com/y/84085/Average-Weather-in-Bydgoszcz-Poland-Year-Round>